

Supplementary Materials

Signal Detection for Australian Antivenoms and Tropical Medicines in the TGA Adverse Event Database: A Pre-Registered Disproportionality Analysis

Hayden Farquhar MBBS MPHTM, Independent researcher, Finley, NSW, Australia

Supplementary Table S1. Signals of disproportionate reporting for Set B (tropical-medicine basket)

All 57 signals meeting the conjunction criterion ($PRR \geq 2$, $\chi^2 \geq 4$, $n \geq 3$, $IC025 > 0$, $EB05 \geq 2$) for Set B products.

Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR (95% CI)	ROR (95% CI)	IC025	EB05	Clinical rating
Doxycycline	Ankle arthroplasty	3	325.7 (54.4–1948.6)	326.1 (54.5–1952.1)	5.40	2.07	Noise
Doxycycline	Gastric mucosal lesion	3	325.7 (54.4–1948.6)	326.1 (54.5–1952.1)	5.40	2.07	Plausible novel
Doxycycline	Product monitoring error	3	162.9 (36.5–727.4)	163.0 (36.5–728.7)	4.91	2.04	Noise
Doxycycline	Jarisch-Herxheimer reaction	5	155.1 (49.3–488.4)	155.4 (49.3–489.8)	5.24	4.12	Established
Doxycycline	Pyroglutamic acidosis	8	91.4 (40.1–208.7)	91.7 (40.1–209.6)	5.01	6.95	Noise
Doxycycline	Cauda equina syndrome	4	79.0 (25.2–247.8)	79.1 (25.2–248.5)	4.45	2.92	Noise
Doxycycline	Oesophageal ulcer	11	56.9 (29.3–110.3)	57.1 (29.4–111.0)	4.65	8.81	Established
Doxycycline	Oesophagitis ulcerative	32	51.1 (34.8–75.0)	51.7 (35.1–76.0)	4.88	18.68	Established
Doxycycline	Oesophagitis	48	30.5 (22.6–41.1)	31.0 (22.8–42.0)	4.34	16.45	Established
Doxycycline	Genital ulceration	16	25.2 (15.0–42.2)	25.3 (15.1–42.5)	3.80	8.65	Established
Doxycycline	Pathogen resistance	8	18.1 (8.8–37.2)	18.1 (8.8–37.4)	3.07	4.44	Established
Doxycycline	Hidradenitis	5	17.8 (7.2–44.3)	17.8 (7.2–44.4)	2.78	2.85	Noise
Doxycycline	Photosensitivity reaction	126	17.7 (14.8–21.1)	18.4 (15.3–22.2)	3.78	13.28	Established
Doxycycline	Sputum discoloured	4	16.1 (5.8–44.4)	16.1 (5.8–44.5)	2.50	2.17	Noise
Doxycycline	Intracranial pressure increased	10	16.0 (8.4–30.3)	16.0 (8.4–30.5)	3.01	4.96	Established
Doxycycline	Rales	4	14.2 (5.2–39.1)	14.3 (5.2–39.2)	2.33	2.08	Noise

Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR (95% CI)	ROR (95% CI)	IC025	EB05	Clinical rating
Doxycycline	Nail disorder	11	14.2 (7.7–26.1)	14.3 (7.7–26.3)	2.89	4.96	Established
Doxycycline	Acute generalised exanthematous pustulosis	7	13.9 (6.5–29.9)	14.0 (6.5–30.0)	2.65	3.52	Plausible novel
Doxycycline	Aspergillus infection	6	13.0 (5.7–29.7)	13.1 (5.7–29.8)	2.47	2.99	Plausible novel
Doxycycline	Fixed eruption	9	12.9 (6.6–25.3)	13.0 (6.6–25.5)	2.67	4.10	Established
Doxycycline	Papilloedema	5	10.2 (4.2–25.1)	10.3 (4.2–25.2)	2.03	2.27	Established
Doxycycline	Completed suicide	23	7.5 (5.0–11.3)	7.6 (5.0–11.5)	2.27	4.41	Noise
Doxycycline	Cytopenia	11	6.6 (3.6–11.9)	6.6 (3.6–12.0)	1.83	2.95	Plausible novel
Doxycycline	Candida infection	12	6.5 (3.7–11.5)	6.5 (3.7–11.6)	1.84	3.05	Established
Doxycycline	Product ineffective for unapproved use	14	6.4 (3.8–10.9)	6.4 (3.8–10.9)	1.88	3.22	Noise
Doxycycline	Toxic epidermal necrolysis	11	6.1 (3.4–11.1)	6.1 (3.4–11.2)	1.72	2.79	Plausible novel
Doxycycline	Drug-induced liver injury	12	5.9 (3.3–10.5)	5.9 (3.3–10.6)	1.72	2.84	Established
Doxycycline	Parosmia	9	5.8 (3.0–11.2)	5.8 (3.0–11.3)	1.56	2.42	Noise
Doxycycline	Metabolic acidosis	9	5.8 (3.0–11.2)	5.8 (3.0–11.3)	1.56	2.42	Plausible novel
Doxycycline	Abnormal sleep-related event	11	5.8 (3.2–10.5)	5.8 (3.2–10.6)	1.65	2.68	Plausible novel
Doxycycline	Toxicity to various agents	62	5.3 (4.2–6.8)	5.4 (4.2–7.0)	2.03	4.06	Noise
Doxycycline	Dermatitis bullous	21	5.1 (3.3–7.9)	5.2 (3.4–8.0)	1.72	3.11	Plausible novel
Doxycycline	Somnambulism	10	5.1 (2.7–9.6)	5.1 (2.7–9.6)	1.44	2.33	Plausible novel
Doxycycline	Drug abuse	10	4.8 (2.6–8.9)	4.8 (2.6–9.0)	1.34	2.21	Noise
Doxycycline	Intentional overdose	16	4.4 (2.7–7.3)	4.5 (2.7–7.3)	1.42	2.50	Noise
Doxycycline	Hepatitis cholestatic	12	4.3 (2.4–7.6)	4.3 (2.4–7.7)	1.27	2.20	Established

Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR (95% CI)	ROR (95% CI)	IC025	EB05	Clinical rating
Doxycycline	Treatment failure	18	4.0 (2.5–6.4)	4.0 (2.5–6.4)	1.32	2.39	Noise
Doxycycline	Dysphagia	48	3.6 (2.7–4.8)	3.6 (2.7–4.8)	1.42	2.68	Established
Doxycycline	Jaundice	30	3.2 (2.2–4.6)	3.2 (2.2–4.6)	1.15	2.21	Established
Doxycycline	Product use in unapproved indication	21	3.2 (2.1–4.8)	3.2 (2.1–4.9)	1.03	2.00	Noise
Doxycycline	Hepatitis	30	3.0 (2.1–4.3)	3.0 (2.1–4.3)	1.05	2.07	Established
Doxycycline	Amnesia	28	2.9 (2.0–4.3)	3.0 (2.0–4.3)	1.01	2.02	Noise
Doxycycline	Face oedema	39	2.8 (2.1–3.8)	2.8 (2.1–3.9)	1.02	2.05	Established
Ivermectin	Hypervitaminosis B6	5	80.4 (38.3–168.5)	82.8 (38.6–177.5)	5.22	6.16	Noise
Ivermectin	Vitamin B6 increased	4	34.6 (13.0–92.0)	35.2 (13.0–95.1)	3.68	2.69	Noise
Ivermectin	Abdominal distension	7	11.3 (5.5–23.6)	11.7 (5.5–24.8)	2.43	3.24	Established
JEV vaccines	Contraindication to vaccination	13	443.0 (246.3–796.9)	463.0 (251.8–851.3)	7.73	15.08	Noise
JEV vaccines	Incorrect route of product administration	26	186.2 (126.8–273.6)	203.8 (134.2–309.6)	6.87	28.59	Noise
JEV vaccines	Oedema mouth	3	74.6 (23.7–234.5)	75.3 (23.7–239.5)	4.54	2.00	Plausible novel
JEV vaccines	Product prescribing issue	5	58.7 (24.3–141.7)	59.7 (24.4–146.2)	4.57	3.89	Noise
JEV vaccines	Injection site inflammation	6	23.0 (10.4–51.0)	23.5 (10.4–52.9)	3.35	3.86	Established
JEV vaccines	Exposure during pregnancy	6	9.9 (4.5–22.0)	10.1 (4.5–22.7)	2.15	2.66	Noise
JEV vaccines	Photophobia	6	9.2 (4.2–20.3)	9.4 (4.2–21.0)	2.04	2.55	Plausible novel
JEV vaccines	Product administered to patient of inappropriate age	7	8.0 (3.8–16.6)	8.1 (3.8–17.2)	1.92	2.63	Noise
JEV vaccines	Vaccination error	23	7.6 (5.1–11.2)	8.1 (5.3–12.4)	2.32	4.54	Noise
JEV vaccines	Urticaria	35	3.4 (2.5–4.7)	3.7 (2.6–5.3)	1.29	2.45	Established

Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR (95% CI)	ROR (95% CI)	IC025	EB05	Clinical rating
Primaquine	Methaemoglobinemia	15	1725.6 (1078.9– 2759.9)	2406.3 (1284.4– 4508.3)	9.83	18.90	Established

Supplementary Table S2. Drug-role stratification masking candidates

Drug-PT pairs meeting the conjunction criterion in the Suspected-role-only analysis but not in the pooled all-role analysis.

Product	Reaction PT	n (all roles)	PRR (all roles)	Signal (all roles)	n (Suspected only)	PRR (Suspected only)	Signal (Suspected only)
Doxycycline	Accidental overdose	13	3.3	False	11	4.6	True
Doxycycline	Clostridium difficile colitis	5	6.4	False	5	10.5	True
Doxycycline	Odynophagia	4	8.6	False	4	14.1	True
Doxycycline	Osteomyelitis bacterial	3	93.1	False	3	152.4	True
Doxycycline	Pseudomembranous colitis	4	11.6	False	4	19.0	True
Doxycycline	Rash erythematous	77	2.3	False	56	2.7	True
Doxycycline	Rash maculopapular	65	2.3	False	52	3.1	True
Doxycycline	Skin exfoliation	18	3.0	False	15	4.1	True
Doxycycline	Therapeutic product effect incomplete	11	3.0	False	10	4.4	True
Doxycycline	Tongue discoloration	4	8.3	False	4	13.5	True
Doxycycline	Tooth discoloration	5	6.2	False	5	10.2	True

Supplementary Table S3. Full scan results for all drug-PT pairs with $n \geq 3$

All 619 drug-PT pairs examined, including both signals and non-signals. Sorted by product set and product name.

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
A	Box jellyfish antivenom	Cardio-respiratory arrest	3	5404.6	10.72	2.16	Yes

Set	Product	Reaction	PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
A	Brown snake antivenom	Hypofibrinogenæmia			36584.0	12.20	2.17	Yes
A	Brown snake antivenom	Underdose		4	226.9	6.40	3.21	Yes
A	Brown snake antivenom	Serum sickness		3	164.8	5.72	2.09	Yes
A	Brown snake antivenom	Cerebral haemorrhage		3	112.2	5.17	2.06	Yes
A	Brown snake antivenom	Anaphylactic reaction		3	6.9	1.15	1.16	No
A	Brown snake antivenom	Drug ineffective		4	6.4	1.26	1.48	No
A	Brown snake antivenom	Urticaria		3	3.4	0.12	0.78	No
A	Polyvalent snake antivenom	Anaphylactic reaction		18	39.8	4.65	12.64	Yes
A	Polyvalent snake antivenom	Bradycardia		3	28.6	3.21	1.79	No
A	Taipan antivenom	Angioedema		3	36.3	3.55	1.86	No
A	Taipan antivenom	Anaphylactic reaction		3	17.9	2.53	1.62	No
A	Taipan antivenom	Urticaria		4	11.7	2.14	1.98	No
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Type I hypersensitivity		6	1031.1	8.76	5.82	Yes
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Anaphylactic reaction		11	16.0	3.15	5.51	Yes
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Erythema		6	13.9	2.64	3.16	Yes
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Hypotension		7	13.3	2.67	3.54	Yes
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Tachycardia		4	6.6	1.30	1.50	No
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Urticaria		9	6.4	1.74	2.66	Yes
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Pruritus		6	4.2	0.90	1.51	No
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Rash		9	4.0	1.06	1.84	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Ankle arthroplasty	3	325.7	5.40	2.07	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Gastric mucosal lesion	3	325.7	5.40	2.07	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Product monitoring error	3	162.9	4.91	2.04	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Jarisch-Herxheimer reaction	5	155.1	5.24	4.12	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Osteomyelitis bacterial	3	93.1	4.40	1.99	No
B	Doxycycline	Pyroglutamic acidosis	8	91.4	5.01	6.95	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Cauda equina syndrome	4	79.0	4.45	2.92	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Oesophageal ulcer	11	56.9	4.65	8.81	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Oesophagitis ulcerative	32	51.1	4.88	18.68	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Drug withdrawal headache	3	32.6	3.20	1.79	No
B	Doxycycline	Oesophagitis	48	30.5	4.34	16.45	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Genital ulceration	16	25.2	3.80	8.65	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Pathogen resistance	8	18.1	3.07	4.44	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Hidradenitis	5	17.8	2.78	2.85	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Photosensitivity reaction	126	17.7	3.78	13.28	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Sputum discoloured	4	16.1	2.50	2.17	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Intracranial pressure increased	10	16.0	3.01	4.96	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Q fever	3	14.5	2.14	1.51	No
B	Doxycycline	Rales	4	14.2	2.33	2.08	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Nail disorder	11	14.2	2.89	4.96	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Infusion site erythema	3	14.2	2.11	1.50	No
B	Doxycycline	Acute generalised exanthematous pustulosis	7	13.9	2.65	3.52	Yes

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Aspergillus infection	6	13.0	2.47	2.99	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Fixed eruption	9	12.9	2.67	4.10	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Oesophageal pain	3	12.5	1.94	1.44	No
B	Doxycycline	Pseudomembranous colitis	4	11.6	2.05	1.93	No
B	Doxycycline	Papilloedema	5	10.2	2.03	2.27	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Pre-eclampsia	3	9.6	1.57	1.31	No
B	Doxycycline	Odynophagia	4	8.6	1.64	1.69	No
B	Doxycycline	Hereditary angioedema	3	8.4	1.38	1.24	No
B	Doxycycline	Tongue discoloration	4	8.3	1.59	1.66	No
B	Doxycycline	Vaginal infection	4	8.0	1.55	1.64	No
B	Doxycycline	Completed suicide	23	7.5	2.27	4.41	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Arteriospasm coronary	3	7.0	1.14	1.15	No
B	Doxycycline	Antinuclear antibody positive	3	6.6	1.05	1.12	No
B	Doxycycline	Cytopenia	11	6.6	1.83	2.95	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Candida infection	12	6.5	1.84	3.05	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Clostridium difficile colitis	5	6.4	1.38	1.76	No
B	Doxycycline	Product ineffective for unapproved use	14	6.4	1.88	3.22	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Tooth discoloration	5	6.2	1.33	1.73	No
B	Doxycycline	Toxic epidermal necrolysis	11	6.1	1.72	2.79	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Drug-induced liver injury	12	5.9	1.72	2.84	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Parosmia	9	5.8	1.56	2.42	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Metabolic acidosis	9	5.8	1.56	2.42	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Abnormal sleep-related event	11	5.8	1.65	2.68	Yes

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Diarrhoea haemor- rhagic	3	5.8	0.86	1.05	No
B	Doxycycline	Nodule	6	5.7	1.33	1.87	No
B	Doxycycline	Methaemoglobin- aemia	3	5.6	0.83	1.04	No
B	Doxycycline	Haemophagocytic lymphohisti- ocytosis	3	5.4	0.78	1.02	No
B	Doxycycline	Toxicity to various agents	62	5.3	2.03	4.06	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Pemphigoid	5	5.3	1.11	1.56	No
B	Doxycycline	Optic neuritis	6	5.2	1.21	1.77	No
B	Doxycycline	Dermatitis bullous	21	5.1	1.72	3.11	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Somnambulism	10	5.1	1.44	2.33	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Hyperaesthesia	6	5.1	1.17	1.74	No
B	Doxycycline	Gingivitis	5	4.9	0.99	1.48	No
B	Doxycycline	Peripheral ischaemia	6	4.8	1.10	1.67	No
B	Doxycycline	Lipase increased	4	4.8	0.82	1.23	No
B	Doxycycline	Product prescribing issue	4	4.8	0.82	1.23	No
B	Doxycycline	Drug abuse	10	4.8	1.34	2.21	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Formication	3	4.5	0.50	0.92	No
B	Doxycycline	Intentional overdose	16	4.4	1.42	2.50	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Haemarthrosis	3	4.4	0.48	0.91	No
B	Doxycycline	Hepatitis cholestatic	12	4.3	1.27	2.20	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Blood iron decreased	4	4.2	0.62	1.13	No
B	Doxycycline	Lip oedema	3	4.1	0.40	0.88	No
B	Doxycycline	Hyperreflexia	3	4.1	0.39	0.88	No
B	Doxycycline	Cheilitis	3	4.1	0.37	0.87	No
B	Doxycycline	Sinus bradycardia	3	4.1	0.37	0.87	No
B	Doxycycline	Glossodynia	3	4.0	0.36	0.86	No
B	Doxycycline	Treatment failure	18	4.0	1.32	2.39	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Therapy change	11	3.9	1.11	1.97	No
B	Doxycycline	Personality change	3	3.9	0.32	0.85	No
B	Doxycycline	Oculogyric crisis	9	3.9	0.99	1.77	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Hepatic steatosis	4	3.8	0.49	1.06	No
B	Doxycycline	Pancreatitis acute	5	3.7	0.62	1.23	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypervolaemia	4	3.7	0.47	1.05	No
B	Doxycycline	Duodenal ulcer haemorrhage	3	3.7	0.23	0.82	No
B	Doxycycline	Rash pustular	5	3.7	0.59	1.21	No
B	Doxycycline	Dysphagia	48	3.6	1.42	2.68	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Ejaculation failure	4	3.6	0.41	1.02	No
B	Doxycycline	Tongue ulceration	3	3.6	0.18	0.80	No
B	Doxycycline	Acne	8	3.6	0.81	1.56	No
B	Doxycycline	Acute hepatic failure	3	3.5	0.15	0.79	No
B	Doxycycline	Akathisia	8	3.5	0.78	1.54	No
B	Doxycycline	Drug reaction with eosinophilia and systemic symptoms	9	3.4	0.80	1.59	No
B	Doxycycline	Accidental overdose	13	3.3	0.94	1.83	No
B	Doxycycline	Oliguria	3	3.3	0.08	0.76	No
B	Doxycycline	International normalised ratio increased	8	3.3	0.70	1.46	No
B	Doxycycline	Blood creatine increased	3	3.3	0.06	0.76	No
B	Doxycycline	Panic attack	12	3.2	0.87	1.73	No
B	Doxycycline	Jaundice	30	3.2	1.15	2.21	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Left ventricular hypertrophy	4	3.2	0.24	0.94	No
B	Doxycycline	Hepatocellular injury	3	3.2	0.01	0.74	No
B	Doxycycline	Product use in unapproved indication	21	3.2	1.03	2.00	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Duodenal ulcer	4	3.1	0.23	0.93	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Bundle branch block right	3	3.1	-0.01	0.74	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypertonia	11	3.1	0.74	1.58	No
B	Doxycycline	Therapeutic response unexpected	4	3.0	0.17	0.91	No
B	Doxycycline	Rib fracture	4	3.0	0.16	0.90	No
B	Doxycycline	Skin exfoliation	18	3.0	0.90	1.83	No
B	Doxycycline	Hepatitis	30	3.0	1.05	2.07	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Pneumonia aspiration	5	3.0	0.29	1.04	No
B	Doxycycline	Therapeutic product effect incomplete	11	3.0	0.70	1.54	No
B	Doxycycline	Amnesia	28	2.9	1.01	2.02	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Respiratory tract infection	5	2.9	0.27	1.03	No
B	Doxycycline	Pain of skin	3	2.9	-0.12	0.70	No
B	Doxycycline	Septic shock	3	2.9	-0.13	0.70	No
B	Doxycycline	Blood glucose decreased	3	2.9	-0.13	0.70	No
B	Doxycycline	Nightmare	22	2.9	0.90	1.85	No
B	Doxycycline	Stevens- Johnson syndrome	11	2.8	0.64	1.49	No
B	Doxycycline	Face oedema	39	2.8	1.02	2.05	Yes
B	Doxycycline	Thinking abnormal	10	2.8	0.57	1.41	No
B	Doxycycline	Mydriasis	5	2.8	0.19	0.98	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypervitaminosis B6	3	2.7	-0.20	0.67	No
B	Doxycycline	Device breakage	3	2.7	-0.21	0.67	No
B	Doxycycline	Neutrophilia	3	2.7	-0.22	0.67	No
B	Doxycycline	Lung disorder	3	2.7	-0.23	0.66	No
B	Doxycycline	Drug resistance	4	2.6	-0.04	0.81	No
B	Doxycycline	Glossitis	4	2.6	-0.05	0.81	No
B	Doxycycline	Tongue oedema	13	2.6	0.57	1.45	No
B	Doxycycline	Rash macular	17	2.6	0.66	1.56	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Multiple organ dysfunction syndrome	5	2.6	0.08	0.93	No
B	Doxycycline	Oral pain	3	2.5	-0.30	0.64	No
B	Doxycycline	Blood bilirubin increased	3	2.5	-0.30	0.64	No
B	Doxycycline	Squamous cell carcinoma	3	2.5	-0.30	0.64	No
B	Doxycycline	Arthropathy	3	2.4	-0.35	0.63	No
B	Doxycycline	Depersonalisation/derealisation disorder	1	2.4	0.11	0.98	No
B	Doxycycline	Hyperprolactinaemia	1	2.4	-0.37	0.62	No
B	Doxycycline	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	5	2.4	-0.00	0.88	No
B	Doxycycline	Abortion incomplete	11	2.4	0.39	1.27	No
B	Doxycycline	Gingival bleeding	3	2.4	-0.41	0.61	No
B	Doxycycline	Rash maculo-papular	65	2.3	0.87	1.86	No
B	Doxycycline	Depression	50	2.3	0.81	1.79	No
B	Doxycycline	Sedation	8	2.3	0.21	1.10	No
B	Doxycycline	Dystonia	18	2.3	0.54	1.45	No
B	Doxycycline	Eosinophil count increased	3	2.3	-0.43	0.60	No
B	Doxycycline	Abnormal dreams	7	2.3	0.13	1.02	No
B	Doxycycline	Mouth ulceration	22	2.3	0.59	1.52	No
B	Doxycycline	Rash erythematous	77	2.3	0.87	1.86	No
B	Doxycycline	Hallucination	38	2.3	0.73	1.68	No
B	Doxycycline	Drug dependence	12	2.3	0.37	1.26	No
B	Doxycycline	Productive cough	6	2.3	0.03	0.94	No
B	Doxycycline	Mouth swelling	3	2.2	-0.47	0.59	No
B	Doxycycline	Haemolytic anaemia	3	2.2	-0.49	0.58	No
B	Doxycycline	Haemoptysis	5	2.2	-0.12	0.83	No
B	Doxycycline	Drug level decreased	3	2.2	-0.51	0.58	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Skin burning sensation	5	2.2	-0.15	0.82	No
B	Doxycycline	Dry skin	6	2.2	-0.04	0.90	No
B	Doxycycline	Conjunctivitis	11	2.2	0.26	1.17	No
B	Doxycycline	Pneumonia	42	2.2	0.68	1.62	No
B	Doxycycline	Dyspnoea exertional	5	2.1	-0.17	0.80	No
B	Doxycycline	Lower respiratory tract infection	24	2.1	0.50	1.43	No
B	Doxycycline	Hepatic function abnormal	41	2.1	0.62	1.57	No
B	Doxycycline	Drug interaction	12	2.1	0.24	1.16	No
B	Doxycycline	Vitamin B6 increased	3	2.1	-0.58	0.56	No
B	Doxycycline	Mucosal inflammation	3	2.1	-0.59	0.55	No
B	Doxycycline	Pharyngitis	9	2.1	0.09	1.04	No
B	Doxycycline	Rash vesicular	7	2.1	-0.04	0.93	No
B	Doxycycline	Flatulence	11	2.0	0.17	1.11	No
B	Doxycycline	Tachypnoea	5	2.0	-0.24	0.77	No
B	Doxycycline	Euphoric mood	3	2.0	-0.62	0.55	No
B	Doxycycline	Liver function test abnormal	18	2.0	0.34	1.28	No
B	Doxycycline	Rash morbilliform	6	2.0	-0.16	0.84	No
B	Doxycycline	Anosmia	3	2.0	-0.65	0.54	No
B	Doxycycline	Muscle tightness	4	2.0	-0.44	0.66	No
B	Doxycycline	Drug hypersensitivity	5	2.0	-0.29	0.75	No
B	Doxycycline	Lupus-like syndrome	3	2.0	-0.66	0.53	No
B	Doxycycline	Retained products of conception	10	2.0	0.07	1.03	No
B	Doxycycline	Cardiac failure congestive	3	2.0	-0.68	0.53	No
B	Doxycycline	Purpura	14	1.9	0.20	1.15	No
B	Doxycycline	Respiratory rate increased	3	1.9	-0.68	0.53	No
B	Doxycycline	Skin lesion	3	1.9	-0.69	0.53	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Glomerular filtration rate decreased	4	1.9	-0.47	0.64	No
B	Doxycycline	Dyspepsia	25	1.9	0.36	1.31	No
B	Doxycycline	Joint stiffness	4	1.9	-0.49	0.64	No
B	Doxycycline	Respiratory distress	4	1.9	-0.49	0.64	No
B	Doxycycline	Off label use	56	1.9	0.53	1.48	No
B	Doxycycline	No adverse event	3	1.9	-0.73	0.51	No
B	Doxycycline	Extrasystoles	4	1.9	-0.51	0.63	No
B	Doxycycline	Oral herpes	3	1.9	-0.74	0.51	No
B	Doxycycline	Oedema peripheral	25	1.8	0.32	1.26	No
B	Doxycycline	Liver injury	3	1.8	-0.75	0.51	No
B	Doxycycline	Inflammation	7	1.8	-0.20	0.84	No
B	Doxycycline	Eosinophilia	8	1.8	-0.14	0.88	No
B	Doxycycline	Infection	13	1.8	0.07	1.05	No
B	Doxycycline	Red blood cell sedimentation rate increased	4	1.8	-0.56	0.61	No
B	Doxycycline	Pollakiuria	8	1.8	-0.17	0.87	No
B	Doxycycline	Sinusitis	6	1.8	-0.33	0.76	No
B	Doxycycline	Pruritus	181	1.8	0.61	1.55	No
B	Doxycycline	Eructation	3	1.8	-0.81	0.49	No
B	Doxycycline	Suicidal ideation	23	1.8	0.22	1.19	No
B	Doxycycline	Paralysis	3	1.8	-0.82	0.49	No
B	Doxycycline	Melaena	11	1.8	-0.05	0.96	No
B	Doxycycline	Stridor	4	1.7	-0.62	0.59	No
B	Doxycycline	Colitis	7	1.7	-0.29	0.80	No
B	Doxycycline	Stomatitis	5	1.7	-0.49	0.67	No
B	Doxycycline	Angioedema	41	1.7	0.33	1.28	No
B	Doxycycline	Ageusia	10	1.7	-0.13	0.91	No
B	Doxycycline	Restless legs syndrome	3	1.7	-0.87	0.48	No
B	Doxycycline	Dry mouth	18	1.7	0.10	1.08	No
B	Doxycycline	Delusion	4	1.7	-0.67	0.57	No
B	Doxycycline	Thrombocytopenia	4	1.7	0.25	1.22	No
B	Doxycycline	Dysuria	5	1.7	-0.53	0.65	No
B	Doxycycline	Abnormal behaviour	7	1.7	-0.34	0.77	No
B	Doxycycline	Erythema multiforme	7	1.7	-0.35	0.77	No
B	Doxycycline	Blister	9	1.6	-0.23	0.85	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Prothrombin level decreased	4	1.6	-0.71	0.56	No
B	Doxycycline	Body temperature increased	6	1.6	-0.47	0.70	No
B	Doxycycline	Hallucination, auditory	4	1.6	-0.74	0.55	No
B	Doxycycline	Periorbital oedema	12	1.6	-0.15	0.91	No
B	Doxycycline	Oedema	14	1.6	-0.09	0.95	No
B	Doxycycline	Petechiae	5	1.6	-0.61	0.62	No
B	Doxycycline	Rash	251	1.6	0.48	1.41	No
B	Doxycycline	Speech disorder	7	1.6	-0.42	0.73	No
B	Doxycycline	Blood alkaline phosphatase increased	3	1.6	-0.99	0.45	No
B	Doxycycline	Mood altered	4	1.6	-0.78	0.54	No
B	Doxycycline	Renal impairment	22	1.6	0.03	1.04	No
B	Doxycycline	Erectile dysfunction	7	1.5	-0.48	0.71	No
B	Doxycycline	Abdominal pain upper	27	1.5	0.05	1.06	No
B	Doxycycline	Maternal exposure during pregnancy	6	1.5	-0.57	0.66	No
B	Doxycycline	Hyperkinesia	3	1.5	-1.04	0.43	No
B	Doxycycline	Acute kidney injury	24	1.5	0.01	1.03	No
B	Doxycycline	Product complaint	5	1.5	-0.68	0.60	No
B	Doxycycline	Chromaturia	3	1.5	-1.05	0.43	No
B	Doxycycline	Coordination abnormal	4	1.5	-0.83	0.52	No
B	Doxycycline	Dyskinesia	9	1.5	-0.36	0.77	No
B	Doxycycline	Cardiac failure	9	1.5	-0.37	0.77	No
B	Doxycycline	Visual acuity reduced	3	1.5	-1.07	0.43	No
B	Doxycycline	Dysarthria	9	1.5	-0.38	0.77	No
B	Doxycycline	Bronchospasm	17	1.5	-0.14	0.92	No
B	Doxycycline	Serotonin syndrome	5	1.5	-0.72	0.58	No
B	Doxycycline	Bronchitis	3	1.5	-1.10	0.42	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Restlessness	6	1.4	-0.63	0.63	No
B	Doxycycline	Tinnitus	21	1.4	-0.09	0.96	No
B	Doxycycline	Anxiety	41	1.4	0.08	1.08	No
B	Doxycycline	Lip swelling	18	1.4	-0.16	0.91	No
B	Doxycycline	Photophobia	9	1.4	-0.44	0.74	No
B	Doxycycline	Disorientation	8	1.4	-0.50	0.71	No
B	Doxycycline	Ocular hyperaemia	6	1.4	-0.65	0.62	No
B	Doxycycline	Insomnia	44	1.4	0.07	1.08	No
B	Doxycycline	Depressed level of con- sciousness	4	1.4	-0.92	0.50	No
B	Doxycycline	Condition aggravated	26	1.4	-0.06	0.98	No
B	Doxycycline	Burning sensation	11	1.4	-0.36	0.79	No
B	Doxycycline	Retching	4	1.4	-0.92	0.50	No
B	Doxycycline	Musculoskeletal chest pain	3	1.4	-1.14	0.41	No
B	Doxycycline	Respiratory depression	3	1.4	-1.16	0.41	No
B	Doxycycline	Therapy non- responder	3	1.4	-1.16	0.41	No
B	Doxycycline	Gastrooesophageal reflux disease	3	1.4	-0.60	0.66	No
B	Doxycycline	Viral infection	5	1.4	-0.80	0.55	No
B	Doxycycline	Epistaxis	14	1.4	-0.30	0.83	No
B	Doxycycline	Exposure during pregnancy	8	1.4	-0.55	0.68	No
B	Doxycycline	Unintended pregnancy	6	1.4	-0.71	0.60	No
B	Doxycycline	Gamma- glutamyltransferase increased	4	1.3	-0.99	0.48	No
B	Doxycycline	Haemorrhage	10	1.3	-0.47	0.73	No
B	Doxycycline	Disturbance in attention	11	1.3	-0.43	0.75	No
B	Doxycycline	Vaginal haemor- rhage	7	1.3	-0.65	0.63	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypoxia	6	1.3	-0.76	0.58	No
B	Doxycycline	Eczema	4	1.3	-1.02	0.47	No
B	Doxycycline	Lacrimation increased	4	1.3	-1.03	0.47	No
B	Doxycycline	Abdominal distension	10	1.3	-0.51	0.71	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Gastritis	4	1.3	-1.03	0.47	No
B	Doxycycline	Depressed mood	6	1.3	-0.77	0.58	No
B	Doxycycline	Hepatic failure	3	1.3	-1.25	0.39	No
B	Doxycycline	Ataxia	8	1.3	-0.62	0.65	No
B	Doxycycline	Confusional state	40	1.3	-0.07	0.98	No
B	Doxycycline	Blindness	4	1.3	-1.04	0.46	No
B	Doxycycline	Febrile neutropenia	6	1.3	-0.78	0.57	No
B	Doxycycline	Throat tightness	16	1.3	-0.34	0.81	No
B	Doxycycline	Dermatitis	3	1.3	-1.26	0.38	No
B	Doxycycline	Overdose	15	1.3	-0.37	0.79	No
B	Doxycycline	Aphasia	4	1.3	-1.06	0.46	No
B	Doxycycline	Abdominal pain	86	1.3	0.05	1.06	No
B	Doxycycline	Platelet count decreased	5	1.3	-0.92	0.52	No
B	Doxycycline	Swollen tongue	14	1.3	-0.41	0.77	No
B	Doxycycline	Rectal haemorrhage	7	1.3	-0.73	0.60	No
B	Doxycycline	Rheumatoid arthritis	3	1.3	-1.29	0.38	No
B	Doxycycline	Product substitution issue	5	1.3	-0.93	0.51	No
B	Doxycycline	Weight decreased	17	1.3	-0.35	0.80	No
B	Doxycycline	Swelling face	17	1.3	-0.35	0.80	No
B	Doxycycline	Urinary retention	5	1.3	-0.94	0.51	No
B	Doxycycline	Breast pain	4	1.3	-1.09	0.45	No
B	Doxycycline	Constipation	19	1.2	-0.33	0.82	No
B	Doxycycline	Dysphonia	8	1.2	-0.68	0.63	No
B	Doxycycline	Agitation	25	1.2	-0.25	0.86	No
B	Doxycycline	Haematuria	6	1.2	-0.84	0.55	No
B	Doxycycline	Hot flush	13	1.2	-0.48	0.73	No
B	Doxycycline	Urticaria	122	1.2	0.04	1.05	No
B	Doxycycline	Pancytopenia	7	1.2	-0.78	0.58	No
B	Doxycycline	Balance disorder	9	1.2	-0.65	0.64	No
B	Doxycycline	Rash pruritic	23	1.2	-0.31	0.83	No
B	Doxycycline	Disease recurrence	4	1.2	-1.14	0.44	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Joint swelling	7	1.2	-0.80	0.58	No
B	Doxycycline	Abdominal discomfort	10	1.2	-0.63	0.66	No
B	Doxycycline	Hepatotoxicity	3	1.2	-1.37	0.36	No
B	Doxycycline	Asthenia	32	1.2	-0.24	0.87	No
B	Doxycycline	Arthritis	7	1.2	-0.83	0.56	No
B	Doxycycline	Visual impairment	23	1.2	-0.35	0.81	No
B	Doxycycline	Psoriasis	4	1.2	-1.18	0.43	No
B	Doxycycline	Product dose omission issue	7	1.2	-0.84	0.56	No
B	Doxycycline	Blood creatinine increased	4	1.2	-1.18	0.43	No
B	Doxycycline	Coma	3	1.2	-1.41	0.35	No
B	Doxycycline	Somnolence	31	1.2	-0.29	0.84	No
B	Doxycycline	Haematemesis	6	1.2	-0.94	0.52	No
B	Doxycycline	Pulmonary oedema	4	1.2	-1.20	0.42	No
B	Doxycycline	Asthma	9	1.2	-0.73	0.61	No
B	Doxycycline	Sepsis	9	1.2	-0.73	0.61	No
B	Doxycycline	Mobility decreased	5	1.2	-1.06	0.47	No
B	Doxycycline	Neuropathy peripheral	11	1.2	-0.65	0.65	No
B	Doxycycline	Affect lability	3	1.1	-1.43	0.35	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypokalaemia	5	1.1	-1.07	0.47	No
B	Doxycycline	Nausea	213	1.1	-0.03	1.00	No
B	Doxycycline	Neutropenia	34	1.1	-0.32	0.83	No
B	Doxycycline	Gait disturbance	13	1.1	-0.62	0.67	No
B	Doxycycline	Drug ineffective	78	1.1	-0.16	0.92	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypoaesthesia oral	3	1.1	-1.50	0.34	No
B	Doxycycline	Anaemia	11	1.1	-0.72	0.62	No
B	Doxycycline	Muscle twitching	8	1.1	-0.87	0.56	No
B	Doxycycline	Pain	46	1.1	-0.28	0.85	No
B	Doxycycline	Sleep disorder	7	1.1	-0.94	0.53	No
B	Doxycycline	Suicide attempt	5	1.1	-1.14	0.45	No
B	Doxycycline	Hyperhidrosis	44	1.1	-0.31	0.83	No
B	Doxycycline	Pleural effusion	4	1.1	-1.30	0.40	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Atrial fibrillation	10	1.1	-0.79	0.59	No
B	Doxycycline	Dehydration	9	1.1	-0.84	0.57	No
B	Doxycycline	Diarrhoea	95	1.1	-0.19	0.90	No
B	Doxycycline	Haemoglobin decreased	6	1.1	-1.07	0.48	No
B	Doxycycline	Unresponsive to stimuli	4	1.1	-1.33	0.39	No
B	Doxycycline	Alanine aminotransferase increased	4	1.1	-1.33	0.39	No
B	Doxycycline	Cellulitis	8	1.1	-0.92	0.54	No
B	Doxycycline	Psychotic disorder	7	1.1	-0.99	0.51	No
B	Doxycycline	Tremor	35	1.1	-0.41	0.78	No
B	Doxycycline	Haematochezia	4	1.1	-1.34	0.39	No
B	Doxycycline	White blood cell count increased	6	1.0	-1.09	0.47	No
B	Doxycycline	Anaphylactic reaction	51	1.0	-0.33	0.82	No
B	Doxycycline	Renal failure	5	1.0	-1.21	0.43	No
B	Doxycycline	Urinary incontinence	5	1.0	-1.21	0.43	No
B	Doxycycline	Intermenstrual bleeding	3	1.0	-1.58	0.32	No
B	Doxycycline	Peripheral swelling	16	1.0	-0.66	0.65	No
B	Doxycycline	Skin discoloration	4	1.0	-1.37	0.38	No
B	Doxycycline	Salivary hypersecretion	3	1.0	-1.61	0.31	No
B	Doxycycline	Nasopharyngitis	6	1.0	-1.14	0.46	No
B	Doxycycline	Rash papular	3	1.0	-1.62	0.31	No
B	Doxycycline	Delirium	7	1.0	-1.05	0.49	No
B	Doxycycline	Dysgeusia	14	1.0	-0.74	0.62	No
B	Doxycycline	Therapeutic response decreased	4	1.0	-1.40	0.37	No
B	Doxycycline	Pneumonitis	4	1.0	-1.41	0.37	No
B	Doxycycline	Liver function test increased	5	1.0	-1.26	0.42	No
B	Doxycycline	Upper respiratory tract infection	3	1.0	-1.63	0.31	No
B	Doxycycline	Vertigo	15	1.0	-0.74	0.62	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Paraesthesia	67	1.0	-0.36	0.80	No
B	Doxycycline	Choking	3	1.0	-1.66	0.31	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypersensitivity	22	1.0	-0.64	0.66	No
B	Doxycycline	Respiratory failure	3	1.0	-1.68	0.30	No
B	Doxycycline	Aggression	9	1.0	-0.99	0.52	No
B	Doxycycline	Malaise	71	1.0	-0.40	0.78	No
B	Doxycycline	Vomiting	117	1.0	-0.32	0.82	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypocalcaemia	3	1.0	-1.70	0.30	No
B	Doxycycline	Contusion	9	1.0	-1.01	0.51	No
B	Doxycycline	Vision blurred	19	0.9	-0.74	0.62	No
B	Doxycycline	Thirst	3	0.9	-1.72	0.29	No
B	Doxycycline	Extrapyramidal disorder	3	0.9	-1.73	0.29	No
B	Doxycycline	Migraine	15	0.9	-0.83	0.58	No
B	Doxycycline	Rhabdomyolysis	4	0.9	-1.53	0.34	No
B	Doxycycline	Decreased appetite	30	0.9	-0.64	0.66	No
B	Doxycycline	Erythema	28	0.9	-0.67	0.65	No
B	Doxycycline	Adverse event	7	0.9	-1.21	0.44	No
B	Doxycycline	Nervousness	4	0.9	-1.56	0.34	No
B	Doxycycline	Feeling hot	14	0.9	-0.90	0.55	No
B	Doxycycline	Cardiomyopathy	4	0.9	-1.57	0.34	No
B	Doxycycline	Alopecia	9	0.9	-1.10	0.48	No
B	Doxycycline	Oropharyngeal pain	15	0.9	-0.89	0.56	No
B	Doxycycline	Feeling of body temperature change	3	0.9	-1.79	0.28	No
B	Doxycycline	Muscular weakness	12	0.9	-0.98	0.52	No
B	Doxycycline	Bone pain	3	0.9	-1.79	0.28	No
B	Doxycycline	Tubulointerstitial nephritis	1	0.9	-1.82	0.28	No
B	Doxycycline	Anaphylactoid reaction	6	0.9	-1.35	0.40	No
B	Doxycycline	Pancreatitis	7	0.9	-1.27	0.43	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypoaesthesia	21	0.9	-0.82	0.59	No
B	Doxycycline	Dyspnoea	108	0.9	-0.48	0.73	No
B	Doxycycline	C-reactive protein increased	7	0.9	-1.29	0.42	No
B	Doxycycline	Generalised tonic-clonic seizure	4	0.9	-1.63	0.32	No
B	Doxycycline	Hyponatraemia	10	0.9	-1.12	0.48	No
B	Doxycycline	Eye swelling	5	0.9	-1.49	0.36	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Fall	15	0.9	-0.96	0.53	No
B	Doxycycline	Back pain	24	0.8	-0.82	0.59	No
B	Doxycycline	Paraesthesia oral	9	0.8	-1.19	0.45	No
B	Doxycycline	Pericardial effusion	3	0.8	-1.90	0.26	No
B	Doxycycline	Wheezing	8	0.8	-1.26	0.43	No
B	Doxycycline	Flushing	28	0.8	-0.81	0.59	No
B	Doxycycline	Pharyngeal swelling	5	0.8	-1.54	0.35	No
B	Doxycycline	Agranulocytosis ³		0.8	-1.92	0.26	No
B	Doxycycline	Weight increased	10	0.8	-1.19	0.45	No
B	Doxycycline	Hyperglycaemia ⁸		0.8	-1.93	0.26	No
B	Doxycycline	Cold sweat	8	0.8	-1.30	0.42	No
B	Doxycycline	Drug level increased	3	0.8	-1.95	0.26	No
B	Doxycycline	Tachycardia	34	0.8	-0.83	0.58	No
B	Doxycycline	Feeling abnormal	9	0.8	-1.30	0.42	No
B	Doxycycline	Musculoskeletal ⁷ stiffness		0.8	-1.44	0.38	No
B	Doxycycline	Rhinitis	4	0.8	-1.80	0.29	No
B	Doxycycline	Blood pressure increased	9	0.8	-1.36	0.41	No
B	Doxycycline	Electrocardiogram QT prolonged	4	0.7	-1.85	0.28	No
B	Doxycycline	Dizziness	98	0.7	-0.75	0.61	No
B	Doxycycline	Memory impairment	4	0.7	-1.89	0.27	No
B	Doxycycline	Disease progression	14	0.7	-1.25	0.44	No
B	Doxycycline	Cough	33	0.7	-0.99	0.52	No
B	Doxycycline	Eye pain	6	0.7	-1.66	0.33	No
B	Doxycycline	Neck pain	7	0.7	-1.59	0.34	No
B	Doxycycline	Cataract	3	0.7	-2.16	0.22	No
B	Doxycycline	Chest pain	72	0.7	-0.87	0.56	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypotension	25	0.7	-1.14	0.47	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypoglycaemia ⁴		0.7	-1.99	0.26	No
B	Doxycycline	Product use issue	4	0.6	-2.06	0.25	No
B	Doxycycline	Heart rate increased	8	0.6	-1.66	0.33	No
B	Doxycycline	Palpitations	32	0.6	-1.19	0.45	No
B	Doxycycline	Pallor	11	0.6	-1.55	0.36	No
B	Doxycycline	Muscle spasms	11	0.6	-1.57	0.35	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Gravitational oedema	3	0.6	-2.36	0.20	No
B	Doxycycline	Application site reaction	8	0.6	-1.79	0.30	No
B	Doxycycline	Cyanosis	3	0.6	-2.42	0.19	No
B	Doxycycline	Hypertension	17	0.6	-1.48	0.38	No
B	Doxycycline	Seizure	16	0.6	-1.50	0.37	No
B	Doxycycline	Cardiac disorder	4	0.6	-2.25	0.22	No
B	Doxycycline	Creatine kinase increased	5	0.5	-2.17	0.23	No
B	Doxycycline	Neutrophil count decreased	3	0.5	-2.55	0.18	No
B	Doxycycline	Gastrointestinal haemorrhage	4	0.5	-2.34	0.21	No
B	Doxycycline	White blood cell count decreased	5	0.5	-2.20	0.23	No
B	Doxycycline	Urinary tract infection	4	0.5	-2.38	0.20	No
B	Doxycycline	Fatigue	66	0.5	-1.32	0.41	No
B	Doxycycline	Deep vein thrombosis	6	0.5	-2.17	0.23	No
B	Doxycycline	Headache	117	0.5	-1.31	0.41	No
B	Doxycycline	Arthralgia	45	0.5	-1.51	0.36	No
B	Doxycycline	Pulmonary embolism	7	0.5	-2.16	0.23	No
B	Doxycycline	Feeling cold	3	0.5	-2.73	0.16	No
B	Doxycycline	COVID-19	3	0.5	-2.74	0.16	No
B	Doxycycline	Brain fog	3	0.4	-2.86	0.14	No
B	Doxycycline	Cardiac arrest	3	0.4	-2.87	0.14	No
B	Doxycycline	Syncope	19	0.4	-1.89	0.28	No
B	Doxycycline	Swelling	5	0.4	-2.56	0.18	No
B	Doxycycline	Concomitant disease aggravated	6	0.4	-2.48	0.19	No
B	Doxycycline	Pain in extremity	19	0.4	-1.98	0.27	No
B	Doxycycline	Chest discomfort	16	0.4	-2.04	0.26	No
B	Doxycycline	Lymphadenopathy	4	0.4	-2.11	0.24	No
B	Doxycycline	Crying	4	0.4	-2.80	0.15	No
B	Doxycycline	Loss of consciousness	4	0.4	-2.84	0.15	No
B	Doxycycline	Rhinorrhoea	3	0.4	-3.13	0.12	No
B	Doxycycline	Pyrexia	64	0.3	-1.99	0.26	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Doxycycline	Myalgia	43	0.3	-2.09	0.24	No
B	Doxycycline	Chills	23	0.3	-2.39	0.20	No
B	Doxycycline	Bradycardia	3	0.3	-3.55	0.09	No
B	Doxycycline	Influenza like illness	8	0.2	-3.05	0.13	No
B	Doxycycline	Myocarditis	4	0.2	-3.65	0.09	No
B	Doxycycline	Irritability	3	0.2	-3.96	0.07	No
B	Doxycycline	Inappropriate schedule of product administration	3	0.2	-3.98	0.07	No
B	Doxycycline	Presyncope	4	0.2	-3.79	0.08	No
B	Doxycycline	Lethargy	15	0.2	-3.29	0.11	No
B	Doxycycline	Injection site pain	5	0.1	-4.26	0.06	No
B	Doxycycline	Injection site reaction	4	0.0	-6.67	0.01	No
B	Ivermectin	Hypervitaminosis B6	5	80.4	5.22	6.16	Yes
B	Ivermectin	Vitamin B6 increased	4	34.6	3.68	2.69	Yes
B	Ivermectin	Myopathy	3	12.8	2.04	1.48	No
B	Ivermectin	Abdominal distension	7	11.3	2.43	3.24	Yes
B	Ivermectin	Alanine aminotransferase increased	3	9.9	1.66	1.35	No
B	Ivermectin	Ocular hyperaemia	3	8.8	1.50	1.29	No
B	Ivermectin	Gastrooesophageal reflux disease	3	7.4	1.25	1.19	No
B	Ivermectin	Liver function test abnormal	5	6.9	1.53	1.87	No
B	Ivermectin	Neuropathy peripheral	5	6.5	1.43	1.80	No
B	Ivermectin	Disturbance in attention	4	6.0	1.18	1.43	No
B	Ivermectin	Gait disturbance	5	5.3	1.15	1.59	No
B	Ivermectin	Brain fog	3	5.3	0.76	1.01	No
B	Ivermectin	Abdominal pain upper	7	4.8	1.20	1.86	No
B	Ivermectin	Photosensitivity reaction	3	4.8	0.64	0.97	No
B	Ivermectin	Burning sensation	3	4.7	0.61	0.96	No
B	Ivermectin	Dry mouth	4	4.7	0.81	1.22	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Ivermectin	Dysphagia	5	4.6	0.92	1.43	No
B	Ivermectin	Jaundice	3	3.9	0.34	0.86	No
B	Ivermectin	Acute kidney injury	5	3.9	0.69	1.28	No
B	Ivermectin	Hypersensitivity	7	3.8	0.87	1.56	No
B	Ivermectin	Off label use	9	3.7	0.96	1.74	No
B	Ivermectin	Weight decreased	4	3.7	0.46	1.05	No
B	Ivermectin	Hepatitis	3	3.7	0.24	0.82	No
B	Ivermectin	Anxiety	8	3.5	0.79	1.54	No
B	Ivermectin	Throat tightness	3	3.0	-0.05	0.72	No
B	Ivermectin	Muscle spasms	4	2.7	0.04	0.85	No
B	Ivermectin	Application site reaction	3	2.7	-0.20	0.67	No
B	Ivermectin	Condition aggravated	4	2.7	0.01	0.83	No
B	Ivermectin	Decreased appetite	7	2.6	0.33	1.15	No
B	Ivermectin	Hepatic function abnormal	4	2.5	-0.08	0.80	No
B	Ivermectin	Feeling hot	3	2.4	-0.38	0.62	No
B	Ivermectin	Insomnia	6	2.4	0.10	0.98	No
B	Ivermectin	Paraesthesia	13	2.4	0.47	1.36	No
B	Ivermectin	Hyperhidrosis	7	2.1	0.03	0.96	No
B	Ivermectin	Malaise	12	2.0	0.19	1.13	No
B	Ivermectin	Diarrhoea	14	2.0	0.21	1.15	No
B	Ivermectin	Pneumonia	3	1.9	-0.70	0.52	No
B	Ivermectin	Anaphylactic reaction	7	1.8	-0.24	0.82	No
B	Ivermectin	Pain	6	1.8	-0.33	0.76	No
B	Ivermectin	Hypotension	5	1.7	-0.53	0.65	No
B	Ivermectin	Abdominal pain	9	1.7	-0.21	0.85	No
B	Ivermectin	Erythema	4	1.6	-0.72	0.56	No
B	Ivermectin	Confusional state	4	1.6	-0.73	0.55	No
B	Ivermectin	Flushing	4	1.5	-0.87	0.51	No
B	Ivermectin	Vomiting	14	1.4	-0.25	0.85	No
B	Ivermectin	Asthenia	3	1.4	-1.16	0.41	No
B	Ivermectin	Pruritus	11	1.3	-0.44	0.74	No
B	Ivermectin	Back pain	3	1.3	-1.25	0.39	No
B	Ivermectin	Neutropenia	3	1.2	-1.34	0.37	No
B	Ivermectin	Nausea	18	1.2	-0.43	0.76	No
B	Ivermectin	Influenza like illness	3	1.1	-1.47	0.34	No
B	Ivermectin	Dyspnoea	11	1.1	-0.73	0.62	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	Ivermectin	Drug ineffective	6	1.1	-1.07	0.48	No
B	Ivermectin	Urticaria	8	1.0	-1.00	0.51	No
B	Ivermectin	Chest discomfort	3	0.9	-1.76	0.29	No
B	Ivermectin	Fatigue	9	0.9	-1.16	0.46	No
B	Ivermectin	Cough	3	0.8	-1.96	0.25	No
B	Ivermectin	Arthralgia	6	0.8	-1.52	0.36	No
B	Ivermectin	Dizziness	8	0.7	-1.45	0.38	No
B	Ivermectin	Palpitations	3	0.7	-2.11	0.23	No
B	Ivermectin	Myalgia	6	0.5	-2.02	0.26	No
B	Ivermectin	Rash	6	0.5	-2.26	0.22	No
B	Ivermectin	Headache	9	0.5	-2.06	0.25	No
B	Ivermectin	Pyrexia	6	0.4	-2.58	0.18	No
B	JEV vaccines	Contraindication to vaccination	3	443.0	7.73	15.08	Yes
B	JEV vaccines	Incorrect route of product administration	26	186.2	6.87	28.59	Yes
B	JEV vaccines	Oedema mouth	3	74.6	4.54	2.00	Yes
B	JEV vaccines	Product prescribing issue	5	58.7	4.57	3.89	Yes
B	JEV vaccines	Injection site inflammation	6	23.0	3.35	3.86	Yes
B	JEV vaccines	Exposure during pregnancy	6	9.9	2.15	2.66	Yes
B	JEV vaccines	Photophobia	6	9.2	2.04	2.55	Yes
B	JEV vaccines	Erythema multiforme	4	9.2	1.78	1.77	No
B	JEV vaccines	Product administered to patient of inappropriate age	7	8.0	1.92	2.63	Yes
B	JEV vaccines	Vaccination error	23	7.6	2.32	4.54	Yes
B	JEV vaccines	Incorrect dose administered	4	7.2	1.42	1.57	No
B	JEV vaccines	Expired product administered	4	6.1	1.19	1.44	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	JEV vaccines	Inappropriate schedule of product administration	7	4.5	1.08	1.75	No
B	JEV vaccines	Overdose	5	4.2	0.79	1.34	No
B	JEV vaccines	Periorbital oedema	3	3.9	0.31	0.85	No
B	JEV vaccines	Peripheral swelling	6	3.7	0.75	1.40	No
B	JEV vaccines	Dysphagia	5	3.6	0.57	1.20	No
B	JEV vaccines	Wrong product administered	4	3.5	0.41	1.02	No
B	JEV vaccines	Face oedema	5	3.5	0.53	1.18	No
B	JEV vaccines	Urticaria	35	3.4	1.29	2.45	Yes
B	JEV vaccines	Injection site pain	13	3.2	0.87	1.75	No
B	JEV vaccines	Neck pain	3	2.9	-0.10	0.70	No
B	JEV vaccines	Oedema peripheral	4	2.9	0.10	0.87	No
B	JEV vaccines	Hot flush	3	2.8	-0.17	0.68	No
B	JEV vaccines	Bronchospasm	3	2.5	-0.32	0.64	No
B	JEV vaccines	Throat tightness	3	2.3	-0.40	0.61	No
B	JEV vaccines	Malaise	17	2.2	0.47	1.38	No
B	JEV vaccines	Headache	55	2.2	0.76	1.72	No
B	JEV vaccines	Asthenia	6	2.2	-0.04	0.90	No
B	JEV vaccines	Lymphadenopathy	8	2.2	0.12	1.04	No
B	JEV vaccines	Paraesthesia	14	2.0	0.25	1.19	No
B	JEV vaccines	Erythema	6	1.9	-0.23	0.80	No
B	JEV vaccines	Pruritus	20	1.9	0.29	1.23	No
B	JEV vaccines	Pain	8	1.8	-0.11	0.90	No
B	JEV vaccines	Influenza like illness	6	1.8	-0.34	0.75	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	JEV vaccines	Rash maculo-papular	5	1.7	-0.47	0.68	No
B	JEV vaccines	Rash erythematous	6	1.7	-0.37	0.74	No
B	JEV vaccines	Hypersensitivity4		1.7	-0.64	0.59	No
B	JEV vaccines	Pyrexia	30	1.5	0.03	1.05	No
B	JEV vaccines	Hyperhidrosis	6	1.4	-0.63	0.63	No
B	JEV vaccines	Nausea	28	1.4	-0.02	1.01	No
B	JEV vaccines	Dizziness	19	1.4	-0.20	0.89	No
B	JEV vaccines	Vomiting	17	1.3	-0.25	0.86	No
B	JEV vaccines	Myalgia	18	1.3	-0.30	0.83	No
B	JEV vaccines	Angioedema	3	1.2	-1.36	0.36	No
B	JEV vaccines	Hypoaesthesia	3	1.2	-1.37	0.36	No
B	JEV vaccines	Diarrhoea	11	1.2	-0.59	0.68	No
B	JEV vaccines	Rash	18	1.1	-0.54	0.71	No
B	JEV vaccines	Somnolence	3	1.1	-1.51	0.33	No
B	JEV vaccines	Insomnia	3	0.9	-1.73	0.29	No
B	JEV vaccines	Fatigue	12	0.9	-0.98	0.53	No
B	JEV vaccines	Injection site reaction	14	0.9	-0.93	0.54	No
B	JEV vaccines	Abdominal pain	6	0.9	-1.36	0.40	No
B	JEV vaccines	Flushing	3	0.9	-1.85	0.27	No
B	JEV vaccines	Chills	7	0.8	-1.31	0.41	No
B	JEV vaccines	Arthralgia	8	0.8	-1.30	0.42	No
B	JEV vaccines	Hypotension	3	0.8	-1.99	0.25	No
B	JEV vaccines	Syncope	3	0.6	-2.26	0.21	No
B	JEV vaccines	Cough	3	0.6	-2.31	0.20	No

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	EB05	Signal
B	JEV vaccines	Dyspnoea	8	0.6	-1.69	0.32	No
B	JEV vaccines	Chest pain	6	0.6	-2.00	0.26	No
B	Praziquantel	Pyrexia	3	4.9	0.65	0.97	No
B	Primaquine	Methaemoglobinemia	1725.6	9.83	9.83	18.90	Yes
B	Primaquine	Cyanosis	3	31.8	3.36	1.82	No
B	Primaquine	Oxygen saturation decreased	3	27.6	3.15	1.78	No
B	Primaquine	Tinnitus	3	11.3	1.86	1.41	No
B	Primaquine	Diarrhoea	6	3.7	0.74	1.39	No
B	Primaquine	Pruritus	5	2.7	0.16	0.97	No
B	Primaquine	Abdominal pain	3	2.4	-0.34	0.63	No
B	Primaquine	Drug ineffective	3	2.4	-0.40	0.61	No
B	Primaquine	Vomiting	4	1.8	-0.57	0.61	No
B	Primaquine	Fatigue	4	1.7	-0.66	0.58	No
B	Primaquine	Dizziness	4	1.6	-0.72	0.56	No
B	Primaquine	Nausea	5	1.4	-0.73	0.58	No
B	Primaquine	Rash	3	1.0	-1.59	0.32	No
B	Primaquine	Headache	4	0.9	-1.56	0.34	No

Supplementary Table S4. JEV temporal analysis

S4a. Quarterly report counts

Quarter	Reports
1988Q1	1
1988Q2	1
1988Q3	2
1988Q4	0
1989Q1	1
1989Q2	3
1989Q3	2
1989Q4	0
1990Q1	2
1990Q2	2
1990Q3	3
1990Q4	3
1991Q1	1
1991Q2	2
1991Q3	2
1991Q4	0
1992Q1	1
1992Q2	1
1992Q3	0
1992Q4	1

Quarter	Reports
1993Q1	0
1993Q2	0
1993Q3	1
1993Q4	2
1994Q1	0
1994Q2	1
1994Q3	0
1994Q4	2
1995Q1	3
1995Q2	0
1995Q3	0
1995Q4	0
1996Q1	2
1996Q2	2
1996Q3	0
1996Q4	5
1997Q1	1
1997Q2	1
1997Q3	3
1997Q4	0
1998Q1	1
1998Q2	5
1998Q3	1
1998Q4	0
1999Q1	0
1999Q2	7
1999Q3	16
1999Q4	3
2000Q1	4
2000Q2	3
2000Q3	5
2000Q4	1
2001Q1	1
2001Q2	2
2001Q3	3
2001Q4	3
2002Q1	1
2002Q2	3
2002Q3	3
2002Q4	1
2003Q1	5
2003Q2	2
2003Q3	0
2003Q4	1
2004Q1	1
2004Q2	1
2004Q3	1
2004Q4	2
2005Q1	0
2005Q2	1

Quarter	Reports
2005Q3	1
2005Q4	1
2006Q1	4
2006Q2	0
2006Q3	0
2006Q4	1
2007Q1	0
2007Q2	0
2007Q3	0
2007Q4	0
2008Q1	1
2008Q2	0
2008Q3	0
2008Q4	1
2009Q1	0
2009Q2	1
2009Q3	0
2009Q4	2
2010Q1	1
2010Q2	1
2010Q3	0
2010Q4	0
2011Q1	1
2011Q2	1
2011Q3	1
2011Q4	0
2012Q1	1
2012Q2	1
2012Q3	2
2012Q4	1
2013Q1	1
2013Q2	1
2013Q3	7
2013Q4	5
2014Q1	2
2014Q2	1
2014Q3	0
2014Q4	2
2015Q1	0
2015Q2	1
2015Q3	2
2015Q4	0
2016Q1	1
2016Q2	0
2016Q3	0
2016Q4	0
2017Q1	0
2017Q2	1
2017Q3	1
2017Q4	0

Quarter	Reports
2018Q1	1
2018Q2	1
2018Q3	0
2018Q4	3
2019Q1	0
2019Q2	1
2019Q3	0
2019Q4	1
2020Q1	1
2020Q2	0
2020Q3	0
2020Q4	0
2021Q1	0
2021Q2	0
2021Q3	0
2021Q4	0
2022Q1	0
2022Q2	2
2022Q3	5
2022Q4	14
2023Q1	7
2023Q2	6
2023Q3	3
2023Q4	8
2024Q1	4
2024Q2	6
2024Q3	4
2024Q4	1
2025Q1	15
2025Q2	12
2025Q3	10
2025Q4	8
2026Q1	6
2026Q2	6

S4b. PELT change-point detection results

Change-point quarter	In H3 window	Pre-change-point mean	Post-change-point mean	Method	Penalty
1999Q2	False	1.29	2.22	PELT	BIC
2000Q3	False	1.82	2.01	PELT	BIC
2004Q2	False	1.89	1.99	PELT	BIC
2013Q1	False	1.50	2.78	PELT	BIC
2014Q2	False	1.58	2.73	PELT	BIC
2021Q4	True	1.36	6.16	PELT	BIC
2024Q2	False	1.60	7.56	PELT	BIC

S4c. Poisson regression coefficients

status	intercept	post_coef	post_irr	post_irr_ci_low	post_irr_ci_high	post_pvalue	trend_coef	trend_pvalue	aic	deviance	pearson_chi2
complete	0.7002	2.1027	8.1885	5.4971	12.1975	0.0000	-	0.0007	587.4333	304.8431	390.9541
								0.0064			

Supplementary Table S5. JEV vaccine PT profile shift analysis (pre-2022 vs 2022-onwards)

PTs that gained signal, lost signal, or appeared/disappeared between the pre-2022 and 2022-onwards periods.

Reaction PT	Pre-2022 n	Post-2022 n	Pre-2022 PRR	Post-2022 PRR	Pre-2022 signal	Post-2022 signal	Shift type
Incorrect route of product administration	1	25	12.5	371.0	False	True	gained_signal
Contraindication to vaccination	1	12	1371.3	225.6	False	True	gained_signal
Exposure during pregnancy	1	5	3.0	15.2	False	True	gained_signal
Pain in extremity	1	0	0.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Optic neuritis	1	0	14.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Oedema mouth	3	0	101.6	nan	True	False	lost_post_2022
Oedema	2	0	3.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Ocular hyperaemia	1	0	3.8	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Nystagmus	1	0	13.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Night sweats	1	0	4.9	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Nasal congestion	1	0	4.3	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Myocarditis	1	0	0.9	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Muscular weakness	1	0	1.3	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Pallor	2	0	1.8	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Muscle twitching	1	0	2.1	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Miliaria	1	0	76.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Migraine	1	0	1.1	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Malaise	17	0	3.6	nan	True	False	lost_post_2022
Lymphadenitis	2	0	37.1	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Lip swelling	1	0	1.3	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Leukopenia	1	0	2.1	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Lethargy	2	0	0.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Musculoskeletal stiffness	1	0	1.9	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Palpitations	2	0	0.7	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Pancytopenia	1	0	2.5	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022

Reaction PT	Pre-2022 n	Post-2022 n	Pre-2022 PRR	Post-2022 PRR	Pre-2022 signal	Post-2022 signal	Shift type
Periorbital oedema	3	0	5.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Weight decreased	1	0	1.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Visual field defect	2	0	17.8	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Visual acuity reduced transiently	1	0	914.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Vision blurred	2	0	1.6	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Vertigo	2	0	2.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Unresponsive to stimuli	1	0	4.9	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Tongue oedema	2	0	5.0	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Thrombocytopenia		0	0.7	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Throat tightness	3	0	4.0	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Swollen tongue	1	0	1.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Swelling face	2	0	2.5	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Swelling Rhinitis	2	0	2.8	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Rash vesicular	2	0	5.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Rash maculo-papular	1	0	4.7	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Rash erythematous	5	0	2.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Prostate cancer	6	0	2.5	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Photophobia	1	0	16.7	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Pharyngitis	6	0	15.0	nan	True	False	lost_post_2022
Intussusception	2	0	6.1	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Insomnia	1	0	12.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Injection site swelling	3	0	1.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Injection site reaction	2	0	2.6	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Disturbance in attention	14	0	1.3	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Dermatitis bullous	1	0	2.0	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Depersonalisation/derealisation disorder	1	0	3.1	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
	0	0	10.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022

Reaction PT	Pre-2022 n	Post-2022 n	Pre-2022 PRR	Post-2022 PRR	Pre-2022 signal	Post-2022 signal	Shift type
Confusional state	2	0	1.0	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Coma	1	0	5.3	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Cold sweat	2	0	3.3	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Circulatory collapse	1	0	3.6	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Chromaturia	1	0	7.8	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Chest pain	6	0	1.1	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Chest discomfort	2	0	0.9	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Bronchospasm	3	0	3.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Bronchitis	1	0	7.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Bradycardia	1	0	1.3	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Ataxia	2	0	4.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Asthenia	6	0	3.6	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Angioedema	3	0	1.8	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Amnesia	1	0	1.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Abortion spontaneous	1	0	4.0	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Abdominal pain upper	1	0	0.9	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Dry mouth	2	0	2.7	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
White matter lesion	1	0	304.7	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Dysaesthesia	1	0	54.9	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Dysphagia	5	0	5.6	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Injection site inflammation	6	0	32.5	nan	True	False	lost_post_2022
Hypotension	3	0	1.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Hypoaesthesia oral	1	0	5.6	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Herpes zoster	1	0	1.5	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Hepatic function abnormal	2	0	1.3	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Heart rate irregular	1	0	5.5	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Haemorrhage urinary tract	1	0	88.5	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Haematuria	1	0	2.9	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Gravitational oedema	1	0	2.5	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Flatulence	2	0	5.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Feeling hot	1	0	1.1	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Fall	1	0	0.9	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Face oedema	5	0	4.6	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022

Reaction PT	Pre-2022 n	Post-2022 n	Pre-2022 PRR	Post-2022 PRR	Pre-2022 signal	Post-2022 signal	Shift type
Extravasation	1	0	65.3	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Extrasystoles	1	0	8.0	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Erythema multiforme	4	0	12.7	nan	True	False	lost_post_2022
Epistaxis	1	0	1.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Encephalitis	1	0	21.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Electrocardiogram abnormal		0	3.2	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Dysarthria	1	0	2.4	nan	False	False	lost_post_2022
Injection site pain	12	1	4.9	0.6	True	False	lost_signal
Urticaria	32	3	5.0	0.8	True	False	lost_signal
Headache	48	7	3.0	0.8	True	False	lost_signal
Lactic acidosis	0	1	nan	15.0	False	False	new_post_2022
Lip erythema	0	1	nan	86.8	False	False	new_post_2022
Molluscum contagiosum	0	1	nan	1127.8	False	False	new_post_2022
Mucosal ulceration	0	1	nan	563.9	False	False	new_post_2022
Noninfective conjunctivitis	0	1	nan	nan	False	False	new_post_2022
Oliguria	0	1	nan	141.0	False	False	new_post_2022
Oral disorder	0	1	nan	94.0	False	False	new_post_2022
Oxygen saturation decreased	0	1	nan	2.6	False	False	new_post_2022
Paraesthesia oral	0	1	nan	2.3	False	False	new_post_2022
Photosensitivity reaction	0	1	nan	17.1	False	False	new_post_2022
Pneumonia	0	1	nan	1.1	False	False	new_post_2022
Product administered at inappropriate site	0	1	nan	5.6	False	False	new_post_2022
SARS-CoV-2 test positive	0	1	nan	3.0	False	False	new_post_2022
Seasonal allergy	0	1	nan	34.2	False	False	new_post_2022
Seizure	0	1	nan	1.2	False	False	new_post_2022
Skin oedema	0	1	nan	282.0	False	False	new_post_2022
Sleep disorder	0	1	nan	2.5	False	False	new_post_2022

Reaction PT	Pre-2022 n	Post-2022 n	Pre-2022 PRR	Post-2022 PRR	Pre-2022 signal	Post-2022 signal	Shift type
Strawberry tongue	0	1	nan	375.9	False	False	new_post_2022
Tachypnoea	0	1	nan	5.7	False	False	new_post_2022
Tongue discomfort	0	1	nan	26.9	False	False	new_post_2022
Vlth nerve paralysis	0	1	nan	70.5	False	False	new_post_2022
Vaccination site erythema	0	1	nan	1.9	False	False	new_post_2022
Vaccination site rash	0	1	nan	8.7	False	False	new_post_2022
Vestibular neuritis	0	1	nan	40.3	False	False	new_post_2022
Wheezing	0	1	nan	2.2	False	False	new_post_2022
Injection site mass	0	1	nan	6.1	False	False	new_post_2022
Injection site discharge	0	1	nan	59.4	False	False	new_post_2022
Shoulder injury related to vaccine administration	0	1	nan	2.7	False	False	new_post_2022
Gait disturbance	0	1	nan	2.2	False	False	new_post_2022
Hyperaemia	0	1	nan	282.0	False	False	new_post_2022
Vaccination error	0	23	nan	5.8	False	True	new_post_2022
Inappropriate schedule of product administration	0	7	nan	3.3	False	False	new_post_2022
Product administered to patient of inappropriate age	0	7	nan	4.7	False	False	new_post_2022
Overdose	0	5	nan	9.2	False	True	new_post_2022
Product prescribing issue	0	5	nan	40.3	False	True	new_post_2022
Incorrect dose administered	0	4	nan	7.6	False	False	new_post_2022
Wrong product administered	0	4	nan	2.2	False	False	new_post_2022
Neck pain	0	3	nan	5.6	False	False	new_post_2022

Reaction PT	Pre-2022 n	Post-2022 n	Pre-2022 PRR	Post-2022 PRR	Pre-2022 signal	Post-2022 signal	Shift type
Wrong technique in product usage process	0	2	nan	6.0	False	False	new_post_2022
Acute kidney injury	0	1	nan	1.7	False	False	new_post_2022
Adverse event following immunisation	0	1	nan	1.9	False	False	new_post_2022
Anuria	0	1	nan	75.2	False	False	new_post_2022
Expired product administered	0	4	nan	4.2	False	False	new_post_2022
Blood glucose decreased	0	1	nan	20.9	False	False	new_post_2022
Flank pain	0	1	nan	18.8	False	False	new_post_2022
Aphthous ulcer	0	1	nan	94.0	False	False	new_post_2022
Feeling of body temperature change	0	1	nan	7.5	False	False	new_post_2022
Electric shock sensation	0	1	nan	9.5	False	False	new_post_2022
Dissociation	0	1	nan	31.3	False	False	new_post_2022
Contraindicated product administered	0	1	nan	13.0	False	False	new_post_2022
Coordination abnormal	0	1	nan	16.3	False	False	new_post_2022
Constipation	0	1	nan	1.8	False	False	new_post_2022
Cerebral haemorrhage	0	1	nan	13.1	False	False	new_post_2022
COVID-19	0	1	nan	0.9	False	False	new_post_2022
Blood pressure increased	0	1	nan	2.2	False	False	new_post_2022
Blood pressure decreased	0	1	nan	5.1	False	False	new_post_2022
Flushing	2	1	0.9	1.1	False	False	stable_non_signal
Chills	6	1	1.1	0.4	False	False	stable_non_signal

Reaction PT	Pre-2022 n	Post-2022 n	Pre-2022 PRR	Post-2022 PRR	Pre-2022 signal	Post-2022 signal	Shift type
Pruritus	18	2	2.6	0.7	False	False	stable_non_signal
Decreased appetite	1	1	0.5	0.9	False	False	stable_non_signal
Erythema	5	1	2.7	0.7	False	False	stable_non_signal
Anaphylactic reaction	1	1	0.4	0.3	False	False	stable_non_signal
Hot flush	2	1	3.0	2.5	False	False	stable_non_signal
Somnolence	2	1	1.1	1.2	False	False	stable_non_signal
Hypoaesthesia	2	1	1.4	0.8	False	False	stable_non_signal
Irritability	1	1	1.1	1.5	False	False	stable_non_signal
Muscle spasms	1	1	0.9	1.5	False	False	stable_non_signal
Oropharyngeal pain	1	1	0.9	1.5	False	False	stable_non_signal
Syncope	2	1	0.7	0.6	False	False	stable_non_signal
Peripheral swelling	4	2	4.6	2.2	False	False	stable_non_signal
Tachycardia	1	1	0.4	0.5	False	False	stable_non_signal
Hyperhidrosis	5	1	1.9	0.7	False	False	stable_non_signal
Paraesthesia	12	2	2.9	0.7	False	False	stable_non_signal
Abdominal pain	2	4	0.5	1.6	False	False	stable_non_signal
Nausea	26	2	2.1	0.3	False	False	stable_non_signal
Tinnitus	1	1	1.2	1.4	False	False	stable_non_signal
Pyrexia	19	11	1.5	1.6	False	False	stable_non_signal
Vomiting	6	11	0.8	2.5	False	False	stable_non_signal
Rash	12	6	1.1	1.2	False	False	stable_non_signal
Arthralgia	4	4	0.7	1.0	False	False	stable_non_signal
Diarrhoea	7	4	1.2	1.2	False	False	stable_non_signal
Dizziness	15	4	1.7	0.8	False	False	stable_non_signal
Myalgia	14	4	1.6	0.8	False	False	stable_non_signal
Dyspnoea	5	3	0.7	0.5	False	False	stable_non_signal
Hypersensitivity Pain	1	3	0.8	2.6	False	False	stable_non_signal
Cough	5	3	2.0	1.6	False	False	stable_non_signal
Fatigue	1	2	0.3	1.1	False	False	stable_non_signal
Influenza like illness	10	2	1.3	0.3	False	False	stable_non_signal
Lymphadenopathy	4	2	1.9	1.5	False	False	stable_non_signal
Oedema	1	2	3.1	0.9	False	False	stable_non_signal
peripheral	2	2	2.0	8.2	False	False	stable_non_signal
Visual impairment	1	1	0.8	1.7	False	False	stable_non_signal

Supplementary Table S6. Signal robustness classification across sensitivity analyses

Number of sensitivity analyses (out of 6 feasible) in which each primary signal was retained. Signals retained in $\geq 80\%$ are classified as robust; $< 50\%$ as fragile.

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	Retained in (of 6)	Retained (%)	Classification
A	Box jellyfish antivenom	Cardio- respiratory arrest	3	5404.6	10.72	5	83%	Robust
A	Brown snake antivenom	Underdose	4	226.9	6.40	5	83%	Robust
A	Brown snake antivenom	Cerebral haemor- rhage	3	112.2	5.17	5	83%	Robust
A	Brown snake antivenom	Hypofibrinogen- haemia	3	36584.0	12.20	5	83%	Robust
A	Brown snake antivenom	Serum sickness	3	164.8	5.72	5	83%	Robust
A	Polyvalent snake antivenom	Anaphylactic reaction	18	39.8	4.65	5	83%	Robust
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Urticaria	9	6.4	1.74	5	83%	Robust
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Anaphylactic reaction	11	16.0	3.15	4	67%	Moderate
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Hypotension	7	13.3	2.67	4	67%	Moderate
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Type I hypersensi- tivity	6	1031.1	8.76	4	67%	Moderate
A	Tiger snake antivenom	Erythema	6	13.9	2.64	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Photosensitivity reaction	26	17.7	3.78	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Toxicity to various agents	62	5.3	2.03	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Oesophagitis	48	30.5	4.34	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Product ineffective for unap- proved use	14	6.4	1.88	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Candida infection	12	6.5	1.84	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Intentional overdose	16	4.4	1.42	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Treatment failure	18	4.0	1.32	4	67%	Moderate

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	Retained in (of 6)	Retained (%)	Classification
B	Doxycycline	Product use in un- approved indication	21	3.2	1.03	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Completed suicide	23	7.5	2.27	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Intracranial pressure increased	10	16.0	3.01	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Oesophageal ulcer	11	56.9	4.65	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Cytopenia	11	6.6	1.83	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Drug- induced liver injury	12	5.9	1.72	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Toxic epidermal necrolysis	11	6.1	1.72	4	67%	Moderate
B	JEV vaccines	Vaccination error	23	7.6	2.32	4	67%	Moderate
B	Primaquine	Methaemoglobin- aemia	1	1725.6	9.83	4	67%	Moderate
B	JEV vaccines	Contraindication to vaccina- tion	1	443.0	7.73	4	67%	Moderate
B	JEV vaccines	Incorrect route of product administra- tion	26	186.2	6.87	4	67%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Hepatitis	30	3.0	1.05	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Jaundice	30	3.2	1.15	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Dermatitis bullous	21	5.1	1.72	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Genital ulceration	16	25.2	3.80	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Dysphagia	48	3.6	1.42	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Face oedema	39	2.8	1.02	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Oesophagitis ulcerative	32	51.1	4.88	3	50%	Moderate
B	JEV vaccines	Product prescrib- ing issue	5	58.7	4.57	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Abnormal sleep- related event	11	5.8	1.65	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Hepatitis cholestatic	12	4.3	1.27	3	50%	Moderate

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	Retained in (of 6)	Retained (%)	Classification
B	Doxycycline	Nail disorder	11	14.2	2.89	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Somnambulism	10	5.1	1.44	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Drug abuse	10	4.8	1.34	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Pathogen resistance	8	18.1	3.07	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Metabolic acidosis	9	5.8	1.56	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Sputum dis-coloured	4	16.1	2.50	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Rales	4	14.2	2.33	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Jarisch-Herxheimer reaction	5	155.1	5.24	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Hidradenitis	5	17.8	2.78	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Pyroglutamic acidosis	8	91.4	5.01	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Acute generalised exanthematous pustulosis	7	13.9	2.65	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Papilloedema	5	10.2	2.03	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Aspergillus infection	6	13.0	2.47	3	50%	Moderate
B	JEV vaccines	Exposure during pregnancy	6	9.9	2.15	3	50%	Moderate
B	JEV vaccines	Product administered to patient of inappropriate age	7	8.0	1.92	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Ankle arthroplasty	3	325.7	5.40	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Cauda equina syndrome	4	79.0	4.45	3	50%	Moderate
B	JEV vaccines	Urticaria	35	3.4	1.29	3	50%	Moderate
B	Ivermectin	Vitamin B6 increased	4	34.6	3.68	3	50%	Moderate
B	Ivermectin	Hypervitaminosis B6	5	80.4	5.22	3	50%	Moderate

Set	Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR	IC025	Retained in (of 6)	Retained (%)	Classification
B	Ivermectin	Abdominal distension	7	11.3	2.43	3	50%	Moderate
B	Doxycycline	Amnesia	28	2.9	1.01	2	33%	Fragile
B	Doxycycline	Parosmia	9	5.8	1.56	2	33%	Fragile
B	Doxycycline	Fixed eruption	9	12.9	2.67	2	33%	Fragile
B	Doxycycline	Gastric mucosal lesion	3	325.7	5.40	2	33%	Fragile
B	Doxycycline	Product monitoring error	3	162.9	4.91	2	33%	Fragile
B	JEV vaccines	Photophobia	6	9.2	2.04	2	33%	Fragile
B	JEV vaccines	Injection site inflam- mation	6	23.0	3.35	2	33%	Fragile
B	JEV vaccines	Oedema mouth	3	74.6	4.54	2	33%	Fragile

Supplementary Table S7. Completed READUS-PV checklist

READUS-PV Item	Description	Manuscript section	Notes
1. Title and abstract	Title identifies the study as a disproportionality analysis; structured abstract reports key elements	Title; Abstract	Title includes “READUS-PV Analysis”; abstract structured with Back-ground/Objective/Methods/Results/Conclus
2. Background and rationale	Context for the analysis, including the drug(s) and adverse event(s) of interest, and why the analysis was conducted	Section 1 (Introduction)	Four objectives stated; rationale for antivenom and tropical medicine product selection; READUS-PV adoption gap identified
3. Objectives	Specific objectives or hypotheses	Section 1, final paragraph	Four explicit objectives enumerated; five hypotheses pre-registered (OSF DOI provided)
4. Data source	Description of the spontaneous reporting database, including name, country, time period, and types of reports	Section 2.1	DAEN identified; full database 1983–2026; 634,149 reports; data fields enumerated; missing fields explicitly noted
5. Data source limitations	Known limitations of the database relevant to the analysis	Section 2.1, para 2; Section 4.6	Missing fields (reporter type, seriousness, outcome, narrative) documented in Methods and discussed in detail in Section 4.6

READUS-PV Item	Description	Manuscript section	Notes
6. Study drugs and comparators	Definition of study drugs, including search strategy, ATC codes, or product dictionary	Section 2.2	15 products in 2 pre-specified sets; product dictionary with search terms locked pre-data acquisition; polyvalent matching rule described
7. Adverse events	Definition and coding of adverse events, including MedDRA version and level (PT, HLT, SMQ)	Section 2.3	MedDRA PTs used; 10,748 unique PTs; MedDRA version ambiguity acknowledged (TGA does not disclose version in public export)
8. Disproportionality measures	Description of the disproportionality measures used, including formulas or references	Section 2.4	Four measures: PRR [12], ROR [13], IC/BCPNN [14], EBGM [15]; 2x2 table construction described; EBGM simplification acknowledged
9. Signal thresholds	Pre-specified thresholds for signal detection	Section 2.4	Conjunction criterion: $PRR \geq 2$, $\chi^2 \geq 4$, $n \geq 3$, $IC025 > 0$, $EB05 \geq 2$; no multiple-testing correction (rationale stated [16])
10. Stratification and subgroup analyses	Description of any stratification or subgroup analyses	Section 2.5	Drug-role stratification (Suspected vs all roles); masking candidate identification method described
11. Time-related analyses	Description of any temporal analyses	Section 2.6	JEV: PELT change-point detection [18] + Poisson regression + time-period-stratified disproportionality; Antivenoms: descriptive yearly counts (no formal change-point per pre-registration)
12. Validation	Description of validation approaches (positive/negative controls, external validation)	Section 2.7	5 pre-specified controls (3 positive, 2 negative); results in Table 2 (5/5 pass)
13. Sensitivity analyses	Description of sensitivity analyses performed	Section 2.9	8 pre-specified (S1–S8); 6 feasible, 2 infeasible (reasons documented); results in Table 3 and Section 3.8

READUS-PV Item	Description	Manuscript section	Notes
14. Interpretation and context	Discussion of findings in context of known safety information, biological plausibility, and limitations of disproportionality analysis	Section 4 (Discussion)	Clinical face-validity review (Section 3.7); signal-by-signal interpretation in Sections 4.2–4.4; limitations in Section 4.8; no causal claims made

Supplementary Figure S1

Figure 1: Supplementary Figure S1. Antivenom yearly report counts by product (1983–2026). Stacked bars show the contribution of each antivenom product to annual reporting totals.

Supplementary Figure S2

Figure 2: Supplementary Figure S2. Drug-role proportion (Suspected) by year, all DAEN reports (1983–2026). The 2021 spike (89%) reflects the COVID-19 vaccine reporting surge.